

MAIN ERRORS OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *This article addresses some of the common problems that arise when translating. He also highlights the current demand for translation studies and its place in society.*

Keywords: *text, translation, vocabulary, terminology, translation problems, transformation, information.*

Introduction

Today, modern globalization and the rapid development of intercultural relations, the expansion of international relations, the development of trade, economic and financial relations between countries, the strengthening of integration processes in Europe and the world, the development of science and technology, the constant exchange of scientific and technical information. Of great importance is the importance of modern languages as factor. Also at the stage of economic, scientific, technical and cultural development, a foreign language is widely used as a means of oral and written communication between different peoples of the world.

As a result of the rapid development of knowledge and technology, translators who have acquired practical skills in translating scientific and technical texts in various fields, as well as in the changing conditions of the modern economy, covering all aspects of the life of modern society -professionals today deserve a special need. Therefore, the need for a wide range of knowledge and specialists is growing day by day.

Thanks to the development of modern technologies, today scientists from around the world have the opportunity to conduct joint research on the exchange of information, and thanks to these means of communication, modern science achieves unprecedented results. In this regard, many manufacturers significantly increase the need for high-quality translations of scientific literature. Translators, on the other hand, must be able to continually translate non-fiction into their vocabulary, improve their ability to understand terms and understand their meaning.

Therefore, when translating scientific and technical terms, the translator must first of all pay close attention to the meaning from a scientific and technical point of view, and then acquire the ability to compare scientific and technical terms

Materials and Methods

In the process of translating scientific and technical texts, the following requirements must be met: translation equivalence, translation accuracy, quality of translation data, quality of translation logic and quality of oral translation. The theory of a foreign language should include knowledge of phonetics, vocabulary and grammatical structure of the language; The practice of compiling scientific and technical texts; Linguistic knowledge (methods of translation, transformation, skills of exchanging verbal equivalents, skills of adding words, skills of terminology, etc.); It is necessary to have extralinguistic knowledge and the ability to use the content and sentences in the process of translating the text (it is necessary to have sufficient knowledge of special scientific and technical translation) One of the main problems of translation is that the translator does not fully understand what "scientific translation" is. abstracts and reviews of articles, diplomas, dissertations and monographs in manuscripts. When translating the above types of work, the following factors should be taken into account: the purpose of the translation, the method of translation, the organization of the text in the translation and the relationship between its parts.

In addition to the structure of academic texts (chapters, sections, paragraphs), there is also its subdivision. For example, in English there are many words and phrases used for various purposes to connect parts of the text, as well as to move from one phrase to another, for example: and, also, besides; although, however, in spite of, in spite of, nevertheless...);

Results and Discussion

Intertextuality is a complex erudite tool used in jotting. This is principally a textbook link within some textbook that reflects the textbook used as a link. Rather of using references from different erudite workshop, intertextuality relies on a conception, rhetoric, or testament deduced from other textbooks to be combined in a new textbook. It could be a retelling of an old story, or you could rewrite popular stories in a ultramodern environment, similar as James Joyce retelling the Odyssey in his veritably popular novel, Ulysses. Although both terms are analogous, their meanings are slightly different because the sign is a short, terse reference that the pen uses in another story without affecting the story line. Intertextuality is grounded on a link to another textbook or a full story.

Conclusion

Not so long ago, computers were considered an amazing invention. Today they are part of our daily life. The novelty of today is virtual reality. The virtual reality

system can take the user to exotic locations such as a beach in Hawaii or inside the human body.

Uzbek translation:

In the past, computers were considered a great invention. Today it is part of our daily life. One of the latest inventions is a virtual reality. The virtual reality system can take users to exotic locations, such as the beach or deep into the Hawaiian Islands.

As we can see from the example, the translation from English into Uzbek was not translated, but underwent a transformation. In other words, the original text is not translated into Uzbek. The transformational model of translation is associated with the idea of "transformational or generative grammar" by the American linguist N. Chomsky. According to this theory, the process of creating a translation is viewed as a syntactic transformation of units and structures of the original language into units and structures of the target language, including the stages and methods of the translation process. Also American-American translators K.Nide, In general, the ideas of transformational theory are one of the most important methods in translation studies in identifying structures and units that are interconnected in translation and interconnected in the process of translation of language pairs.

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